

SUBSTANTIVE PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS WITH A COLOR- DENOTING COMPONENT

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Abstract: There are a lot of phraseological units with a color component in the Karakalpak language. They are an integral part of the language. This thesis discusses the forms of expression in Karakalpak color culture, as well as the reasons for its formation and development. It also examines the types of substantive phraseological units and their meanings in the Karakalpak language. The study aims to understand the symbolic connotations of colors in the Karakalpak language.

Keywords: phrase, phraseological unit, color components, lexical meaning.

Introduction

Finding common and particular variations in the lexical and grammatical composition of phraseology with a tone component in the Karakalpak language is the goal of the research of lexical and grammatical features, which are among the pertinent components of phraseology.

Problems inherent in the grammatical structure of phraseological units have long been the subject of linguistic research.

The fact that we are studying allows us to identify two structural types of phraseological units among phraseological units with a material and expressive component:

- 1) phraseology equivalent to a phrase;
- 2) phraseological units equivalent to words.

In the Karakalpak language, there are very few phraseological units with the word structure. The majority of phraseologisms consist of units formed according to the structure scheme of word chains.

Results and Discussion

Phraseologisms of one kind or another, correlating with various parts of speech, have their own grammatical features: categorical (grammatical) meaning, morphological properties, and typical syntactic function. However, the division of phraseologisms into types is based, first of all, not on the presence or absence of components in their composition that are correlated with one or another part of speech, but on their semantics (Novikov, 1987).

In each type of phraseological unit, the morphological properties of speech organs appear in their own unique form. Phraseologisms can have a complete or incomplete paradigm, and the phenomenon of paradigm deficiency is much more common among phraseologisms than among words.

Undoubtedly, “the specific structural features of languages influence the structural-grammatical structure of phraseological units” (Arsenteva, 1987). The Karakalpak language, which is considered an agglutinative language, is characterized by haplosemia (“a typical meaning”), “the lack of uniformity of formative affixes, that is, the addition of only one affix to each gram, which serves it, and the absence of parallel, identical formal categories, that is, the uniform declension of all nouns, the uniform conjugation, formation of all verbs, etc. (Maslov, 1987); word formation in it is dependent on postfixation, prefixes are not used in the formation of words. There are no prepositions in the Karakalpak language, their function is usually performed by declensional endings; among the characteristic morphological features of the Karakalpak language, it is worth noting the absence of case-number categories in nouns and case-number (vide) categories in verbs.

Taking into account the semantics, grammatically dominant component and syntactic functions of phraseology by A.V. Kunin (1972), A.I. Molotkov (1977) [149] and G.Kh. Akhunzyanov (1974), as well as the internal structural differences of the language under study, we distinguish the following types of phraseology with a color component in the Karakalpak language: substantive, verb, adjective, adverbial. Substantive phraseologisms, denoting an object or a substantivized action, are functionally related to the nouns that are their main components. The main component (substantive) is "a leading, grammatically unnecessary component that belongs to a certain part of speech and determines the function of a phraseologism as a certain part of speech" (Arkhangelsky, 1964). Substantive phraseologisms can be characterized by a person's place in society or by his belonging to a certain social stratum; characterize him in terms of various emotional, evaluative, intellectual and human qualities.

The components of substantive phraseologisms of the studied lexical-semantic group are connected by subordinate relations. Structurally, they are divided into two groups: two-component and multi-component phraseologisms.

Two-component substantive phraseological units are represented by two components: *aq taban* (white paw) "a defeated person whose outward appearance is not only associated with hardship" (лит.: ақ табан), *qara basi* (black head) "only himself, only alone", *qara xaliq*, *qara puxara* (*black people*, *black citizen*) "poor, helpless people", "qara" (black), *aq jay* (white house) "school, educational area", *aq qatıq* (white yogurt) "milk products", *qara júzi* (black face) "qayǵılı júz" (лит.: қара бет), *qara et* (*black meat*) "lean meat" (лит.: қара гөш), *qara mal* (black cattle) "large black cattle" (лит.: қара мал), *qara kóz* (*black eyes*) (лит.: перзент), *qara qaǵaz* (black paper) (лит.: letter, bad letter), *qara kún* (*dark day*) (лит.: hardship, hard times), *qara qazan* (black pot) (лит.: pot), *qara suw* (*black water*) (лит.: simple water), *qara jer* (*black land*) "jer", *qara miynet* (black work) "heavy labor performed by manual labor" black labor "heavy labor performed by manual labor", *qara dizim*,

qara dápter “kind of document”, *qara shúyel*, *qap-qara shúyel* “misery”, *qizil shaqa* (лит.: newborn baby, infant) *qizil sharshi* (red scarf) (лит: women, girl), *sari uwayim* (yellow fever) (лит.: sadness, grief, sorrow), *kók tiyin* (лит: money). For example: Awıldıń shetindegi móldir suwǵa tolıp, kólden teńizge aǵıp turatuǵın japtıń bergi jaǵındaǵı qamıs shomnan buwılıp boy tiklegen, keyin sıbatıp háklenip, awılda birinshi “aq jay” (white house) atanǵan “Taza dáwir” mektebin shólkemlestiriwshi hám basshılıq etken de ózi edi (Z.Ishmanova). Эширбек тәўиптиң көрсетпесине бола тилинген ғарбыздың қып-қызыл шербетин *қара қазанға* (black pot) қайнатып, соннан дүгилдик кесе менен ишип жататуғын, басқа аўқатлардан нәр татпайтуғын еди (Alp Sultan). Шарўаларда бундайда *қара қазанлар* (black pots) гөшке толы қайнайды, дастурханлар кеңнен жайылып, қонақлар қалыўсыз күтиледі, “қылмойын шийшелер”, қаладағыдай биримлеп емес, дастурханның шетине ящиги менен әкелип қойылады (Alp Sultan). Әкесинен *қара қағаз* (black paper) алдым (T.Qayıpbergenov) Аўылдағы *қара суўды* (black water) терис ағызаман, мениң ғарғысыма ушыраған адам оңбайды деген ийшанлар да кетти (S.Bahadirova). – Сизлер де бир күни адам болған соң, бир *қызыл шаршының* (red scarf) изине ерип кетесиз ғой, - деди (Z.Ishmanova) Хаў, аманат дегенди де ярым әсирлеп сақлай ма екен бунша?! Оннанда мына *қара көзлер* (black eyes) пайдалансын! – деп бир мазмундағы сөзди қайталайды хәм оның бет-жүзине қарап нәтийжели жуўап күтеди, үмитленеди (M.Tawmuratov. Тоғай қосығы). Ең әхмийетлиси: аўылдан кеткен еки достың өзге журтларда *қара жерди* (black land) қайра-қайра басып, тири жүргенлиги, фашистлерге хәр бир саўашта ротасы менен аянбастан соққы берип атырғанлығы еди (Alp Sultan). — Билемен, Ақсүңгүл! Бирақ мен әўдийген бойым болмаса, *қара мийнетке* (black work) пүткиллей жарамайман ғой (Alp Sultan). Бул енди оның фамилиясының *қара дизимге* илингенинен дерек берер еди (Alp Sultan). Лекин олардың ишинде атлары *қара дәнтерге* (black notebook) түскенлердің фамилиялары жоқ еди (Alp Sultan). Үш

туўысқан жыйналып елдің бахтын ашыў орнына, маңлайына *қап-қара шүйел* болдық ғой (Т.Қайыпbergenov). Жақсылық *қара пухарадан* (black citizen) шығады (S.Bahadirova). Ақша қайда оған. Үйде *көк тийин* қалмады. Балаларың бир хәптеден берли ыссы аўқат ишкен жоқ (А.Атажанов).

Multi-component substantive phraseologisms are represented by three or more components:

The phraseologisms of the lexical-semantic branch considered are divided into phraseologisms with coordinating relations and subordinate phraseologisms. Phraseologisms with coordinating relations are rare in our language: *aq da bar, qara da bar* “jaqsı da, jaman da bar”, *aq kúnler de , qara kúnler de* “jarıq kúnler menen qara kúnler”, *moynına ala qorjin tústi* “shańaraqlı bolǵan adam, úydiń iyesi” t.b. (there is white and there is black, “there is good and there is bad,” there are both white days and dark days, “light days and dark days,” a basket with a white cloth on its neck means “a person who is bright, the owner of the house,” etc.):

The obligatory (necessary) element of these phraseologisms is considered to be coordinating components. Substantive word sequences with coordinating connections of components are much lower than subordinate connected sequences.

In the Karakalpak language, we will consider substantive phraseologisms, which are considered to be affixes that serve as subordinating conjunctions. Among them, the most common are the -li affix of appearance, which indicates the presence or absence of a certain property, and the most common are the accusative suffixes, which are usually in the III case singular: *aq saqalli* “ǵarrı, shal, aqsaqal”, *qara júzli* “namıssız, tómen adam, insapsız, hiyleker” *qara júrekli* “jaman, zulım, basqalargá jamanlıq oylaytuǵın adam, zulım”, *qara júzli* “qıyanetker (onıń), opasız júz”, *aq kúnli* “jarıq (onıń) kún hám t.b: For examples: Себеби, сиз бюрократсыз, буның дәслепки нышанын сизиң *ақ сақаллы* адамға бармақ шошайтып, “сен” деп, сөйлегениңизден абайлап едим. (Sh.Seytov) *Қара жүрек* Иблистиң тилеги болып, жапакеш ана соңғы сапарынан тез орала алмайды. (G.Esemuratova)

Judging by the component adverbial conjunction in substantive tone-phraseological units, the most common type of structure is the combination of the adverb with the noun: *qara jer* "qábir", *qara kúsh* "qara kúsh" (black earth "grave", black power "black power"): For examples: -Хўў...ў, шырағым-аў, қара басым, *qara жерге* киргенше Турдимуратымды умытарман ба, - деп қолларын зорға көтерип тиркисленген бармақлары менен көзлерин сүртти анам. (G.Esemuratova)

We have listed phraseologisms with a colorative component without a suffix in the Karakalpak language: *qızılı qızıl*, *ağı-aq* "eń lázzetli", *awzınan sarısı ketpegen* (таймаған) "бөпе", "awzınan súti túspegen", *kózleri qarańǵilasıw* "kózleri qarayıp ketiw", *qara júzi* "qayǵılı júz": For examples, Болмаса, еки соқпақ екеўин еки жаққа жетелеп кетеди де, көрпе бир болғаны менен, кеўил қосылмайды, басқа болады, балам. Бул да бир, кәсип таңлағандай, ал, кәсип таңлаў *аўзынан сарысы кетпеген* өзиң қусаған палапанларға, қостар таңлаўдан аңсат емес. (Sh.Seytov)

The majority of substantive colorative phraseological units are two-component or three-component. The first components of the studied phraseological units, as a rule, remain unchanged, while the latter can take on various grammatical forms (case, person, number).

Two-component phraseologisms of the model "appearance + noun in the noun case" are combined with nouns in the noun case, thereby expanding their structural and grammatical capabilities: *aq kúnler*, *qara kúnler*, *qara pul* (*white days*, *black days*, *black money*). For examples: Рустемниң бул қыдырыспасы, дастурхан басында жеңгейлиге айтылған гәплер Гүлмураттың басына қандай *қара күнлер* (black days) туўдыратуғыны сол күни олардың екеўиниң де қыялына келген жоқ. (P.Hojamuratova)

In the studied material, there are a small number of colorative two-component phraseological units that have the structure "appearance + narrative". We found an

example of this group being drunk: *aq nuskен* “я балық емес, я гөши емес” (“Either it's not fish or meat”).

Conclusion.

In short, substantive phraseology with a color component is less numerous in the Karakalpak language than adjectival phraseology. The meanings they convey play a significant role in increasing the linguistic richness of the language. Phraseology with a color component is a clear proof of this. Therefore, it is considered a task for linguists to conduct a large number of scientific works in this area.

Phraseologisms of the Karakalpak language are reflected in the customs, traditions, way of life, lifestyle, culture and nationality of the people.

The people of Karakalpak are mainly engaged in fishing, farming and animal husbandry. They expressed their best wishes to each other in connection with these professions. Phraseological phrases such as let the date become red, let the black increase, let the tree be green are among these.

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RANG BILDIRUVCHI KOMPONENTLI SUBSTANTIV FRAZEOLOGIZMLAR

Annotatsiya: Qoraqolpoq tilida rang komponentli frazeologik birliklar juda kop. Ular tilning ajralmas qismidir. Ushbu tezisda qoraqalpoq ranglar madaniyatining ifoda shakllari, shuningdek, uning shakllanishi va rivojlanishi sabablari, substantiv frazeologizmlarning turlari, bildiradigan ma'nolari muhokama qilindi. Qoraqalpoq tilidagi ranglarning ramziy semalari bor ekanligini tushinib olishdan iborat.

Kalit so'zlar: Fraza, ibora, rang komponentlar, leksik ma'no

СУБСТАНТИВНЫЕ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЗМЫ С ЦВЕТООБОЗНАЧАЮЩИМ КОМПОНЕНТОМ

Аннотация: В каракалпакском языке имеется большое количество фразеологизмов с цветовым компонентом. Они являются неотъемлемой частью языка. В данной тезисе рассматриваются формы выражения цветовой культуры каракалпаков, причины её формирования и развития, виды субстантивных фразеологизмов и передаваемые ими значения. Цель статьи – показать, что цвета в каракалпакском языке имеют символическое значение.

Ключевые слова: Фраза, выражение, цветовые компоненты, лексическое значение